

Effects of Public Debt on Economic Growth with non-linearity in Sub-Saharan Africa: Case of the Countries of the West African Economic and Monetary Union

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This article examines the impact of public debt on economy growth in the West African Economic Monetary Union (WAEMU) region from 2010 to 2019. It does so using data from a panel of eight WAEMU member countries. Using a Panel Smooth Transition Regression (PSTR) model developed by González et al., we establish a non-linear relationship between the influence of public debt on economic growth and the evolution of the debt relative to GDP (2005). The findings show that changes in debt levels have an effect on economic development in both positive and negative directions. The average threshold for this transition is 60.3 %. Our conclusions are substantiated by elements relating to the business environment and the institutional quality.

Keywords: ECONOMIC GROWTH, PUBLIC DEBT, GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT (GDP), WORLD BANK, INTERNATIONAL MONETARY FUND (IMF), PANEL SMOOTH TRANSITION REGRESSION (PSTR), WEST AFRICAN ECONOMIC MONETARY UNION (WAEMU).

1. Introduction

Sub-Saharan Africa has an area of approximately 24,265,000 km² and is home to 48 nations totaling around 1,022,664,451 people. That is, Africa south of the Sahara, excluding North Africa (Morocco, Tunisia, Libya, Algeria, and Egypt). Additionally, it contains forty of the world's fifty most populous nations. As a result, Sub-Saharan Africa's population predicament has a substantial impact on the economy, which is already struggling. Due to a lack of competent governance and ineffective fiscal management measures, Sub-Saharan Africa's

economic position is as dire as it is. As a result, economic growth, gross domestic product (GDP), and GDP per capita have all slowed. This subject interests us because we believe there is a basic lack of political will to achieve genuine economic development. In Sub-Saharan Africa, raw materials (gas, oil, gold, diamonds, and zircons, among others), demography (young and robust inhabitants), renewable resources, and fertile land for developing sustainable agriculture abound. Not to be neglected are the nations that must be included in this boundary along the Atlantic Ocean's shoreline. They also have fishing resources, which should not be overlooked considering their fishing contracts with countries like Korea, Japan, and China. Individuals do not experience or see the benefits of these riches, primarily due to insufficient state management or a collapse of the administrative structure (corruption, bad contracts for the exploitation of resources, etc.). Additionally, there are insufficient strong national enterprises to meet market and government expectations. Given these obstacles, many Sub-Saharan African governments are forced to finance their initiatives through public debt. As a result, debt has become a tool for decreasing fiscal deficits. Numerous governments in Sub-Saharan Africa have financed their investment and recovery programs through public debt. However, who are the lending institutions and countries? Is going into debt a viable method for debt relief? The World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, the Paris Club, and the London Club are all minor lending organizations. This is becoming less prevalent, though, as international and bilateral agreements place a greater focus on borrowing to finance projects. Because China now controls almost all of Sub-Saharan Africa's debt (40% of Africa's debt), China's domination will not deter us.

In the field of public finance, all financial commitments made in the form of loans by a state, its public agencies, and its directly dependent entities are referred to as public debt (certain public enterprises, social security bodies, etcetera). Despite the fact that their earnings surpass their expenditures and their net financial value is generally positive, all nations have public debt. When there is a budget shortage, the loan is used to cover it, resulting in additional and growing debt over time. Today, the most prevalent type of debt is government borrowing from the general populace. Commercial banks, international institutions (World Bank, IMF, regional development banks, and institutes), and other states may make speculative loans. These research questions will help to fully justify this study: What is the significance of the national debt? Why is it critical to inquire about your currency's debt? Why is debt so prevalent? The term "public deficit" refers to a fiscal year in which government spending (state, local, and social security) exceeds revenue. As a result, borrowing is necessary to make up the difference. The total amount of loans extended to support annual government deficits is referred to as the public debt. As a result, the public deficit serves as a source of revenue for the public debt stock. Between 2010 and 2020, the increase in state public debt creates a quandary about how to interpret economic statistics presented in various media (texts, tables, graphs...). It is a subject of "public deficits and public debts in various Sub-Saharan African states," and we have seen that all of the nations' public debts have increased significantly between 2010 and 2020. As a result, several countries in Sub-Saharan Africa have exceeded the widely accepted convergence benchmark of keeping general government debt below 60% of GDP. The total foreign debt of Sub-Saharan

African countries, excluding South Africa, stood at approximately 600 billion dollars at the end of 2018, with 500 billion in long-term debt, 370 billion owed to governmental institutions, and 130 billion owed to private individuals. Between 2008 and 2018, the average public debt of African nations increased from 38% to 56% of GDP. According to the International Monetary Fund, it will reach 64% of GDP in 2020, which appears moderate in comparison to European debt but is extremely high for countries with little financial market credibility. Prior to the outbreak, seven countries were considered probably unable to repay their debts in full, twelve were considered at high risk, and twenty were considered at moderate or high risk, according to debt sustainability assessments conducted by the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank. Private creditors make up a sizable portion of Sub-Saharan African countries' external public debt, putting pressure on debtor governments' budgets; interest rates on these loans are typically far higher than those charged by governmental lenders despite the significantly shorter payback times.

The following are the study's objectives: Consider the following recommendations for maintaining macroeconomic stability: Governments must build on recent accomplishments to further reduce budget deficits and, as a result, the risk of an unsustainable imbalance in public finances that results in debt accumulation, payment difficulties, or an increase in the tax burden, by redefining economic policy and administration functions, improving tax collection, eliminating tax exemptions, and combating coercion. Utilize a fair exchange rate. Overvaluation has a detrimental effect on output and exports, and hence, changing the loan currency might undoubtedly assist in containing debt payments. All of these objectives include restructuring the financial system, establishing central bank independence from the government, establishing an efficient banking system supervision and verification system, and promoting the integration of a competitive private banking system open to international competition. This study will assist us in comprehending both the current stage of evolution and the impact of the national debt. Given the status of Sub-Saharan Africa's economy, particularly that of the West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU). When there is non-linearity in the economy, what effect does public debt have on economic development? This is a critical issue for the West African Economic and Monetary Union's member states (WAEMU). The issue of government debt is a hot topic in economics. For centuries, the consequences of sovereign public debt on the economy have been a central theme in contemporary macroeconomics (and therefore on the various macroeconomic aggregates). The issue of impoverished nations' debt has been a major source of contention in recent decades of international relations. This is now acknowledged as a critical issue in international organizations. The World Bank is committed to achieving its mission of alleviating extreme poverty and fostering development in this manner. The IMF recognizes the issue of impoverished nations' debt as part of its international monetary monitoring mandate. As a result, it appears to be universally viewed as a hindrance to their growth. Emerging countries' foreign debt has risen considerably in recent decades. As a result, research on the role of foreign debt in development finance has become an increasingly important and ongoing topic of study. Debt, like all other economic issues, has an undeniable effect on a country's economic development. The issue is, however, how

this variable affects growth rates, particularly in WAEMU member states. In theory, public debt should enable governments to borrow additional funds to invest in areas where their financial resources are insufficient (Klein 1994). In other words, debt is intended to stimulate overall growth and development.

2 Literature review

While a country's GDP may shrink faster than its debt, the reported debt-to-GDP ratio may decrease even as the nominal amount of debt increases. When public finances are in deficit, it is easy to conclude that public spending is financed through borrowing rather than taxes, resulting in an increase in debt. Checherita-Westphal and Rother (2011) used the econometric method to demonstrate in an economic review titled "the Impact of Government Debt on Growth in the Eurozone" that while public debt does not have a linear effect on the growth rate of gross domestic product per capita in 12 Eurozone countries from 1970 to the present, it can have a negative effect on growth in all countries in this zone. According to Claude Deniau, Fiori, and colleagues (1989), depending on the imported component, an increase in debt can have both positive and negative effects on the current account and money creation. To be certain, though, full capital movement data would be required. In economic news, BENAYED and GABSI (2020) found that internal public debt has not been a substantial impediment to economic growth, owing to banks' lack of investment funding, which can be explained in a variety of ways (for example, weaknesses of state institutions or lack of banks with high income that can support a heavy project). Internal public debt, on the other hand, is more attractive from our perspective due to the lower interest rate. Nersisyan and Wray (2011) argue in an economic analysis that government debt denominated in foreign currencies may be a disadvantage. Simply expressed, this means that the state will have substantial difficulties repaying the debt since it may be powerless in the face of obligations, and this powerlessness stems from the loan being acquired in a foreign currency that it does not completely understand. He will then find himself in a potentially grave financial predicament. As a result, accepting a debt in the debtor's currency is preferable because the payback will be fluid rather than dense. According to Nautet and Meensel (2011), when a government's debt grows at an abnormal rate, there is a significant risk of inflation. This indicates that the government will be accountable for debt repayment; simply making a change will help, but will also result in inflation, which will be felt by the general public. As a result, they continue their analysis by arguing that while a low debt level has no effect on economic development, debt levels between 90% and 100% of GDP severely impair growth. The expansion Public and government-guaranteed debt boost public investment but depress private investment. According to an economic essay written by Pascal De Lima (2016), public debt has a negative effect on interest rates. Interest rates fluctuate in reaction to changes in governmental debt, affecting the borrowing capacity of economic players but also raising investor concerns about a default. Malam (2004) illustrates that state debt has a detrimental effect on total and private investment in Niger. This is because the total amount of government and government-backed debt has exceeded the debt ceiling. As a result, this negative effect is attributed to the state budget's large unsustainable debt, which will generate inflation in order to restore the economy's balance. According to Tille (2019), a constant debt-to-GDP ratio reveals a link between

the primary deficit and the interest-to-growth rate gap" A reduction in public debt results in a large difference between private and public interest rates in Switzerland, thereby narrowing the gap between economic growth and the fiscal surplus required for fiscal stability," he writes. Additionally, an increase in public debt that is wholly reinvested in private assets reduces the spread between private and public interest rates and creates the necessary budget surplus to balance the books. DINC (2013) evaluated the debt-related repercussions in five countries: Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania, and Slovakia, and discovered that these countries' public debts are 44.42%. As a result, as this rate increases, government debt may have a detrimental effect on economic growth. Sania, Said, and colleagues (2019) discovered that the interaction term "institutional quality" and public debt has a significant effect on the debt-growth relationship in 46 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa by examining the impact of public debt and institutional quality on economic growth using the generalized method of moments. As a result, they assert that the effect of debt is determined by the quality of governmental institutions. As a result, they emphasize the need for government efficiency, anti-corruption, and regulatory quality in mitigating the detrimental impact of public debt on the region. Egbe Tunde (2012) concludes in an article published in the American Journal of Economics that the impact of public debt on economic growth will be positive if the government is sincere in its debt financing and views it as a promising and beneficial investment rather than a means to an end; otherwise, the impact will almost certainly be negative. According to AKRAM (2011), debt can be good when used to fund growth in resource-poor countries. As a result, increasing public debt boosts growth while also increasing these countries' capacity to service and repay debt. On the other hand, if excessive debt and foreclosure occur, the effect of public debt may be detrimental. The impacts of debt on GDP per capita and investment in Pakistan from 1972 to 2009 indicate that the country is over-indebted. According to Anning, Ofori, et al. (2016), certain data on the effect of public debt may be incorrect. They continue by stating that government corruption, a malfunctioning administrative system, and other factors may be to blame. As a result, corruption contributes to the detrimental effect of debt on growth, as debt unavoidably slows the economy. As the economy slows, we all know that debt payback calculations will become inaccurate, resulting in repayment issues. They also note, as do many other writers, that while a low debt ratio promotes growth, a high debt ratio is unsustainable, which is why it frequently has a negative influence on economic growth, particularly when the economy is small. SOULAMA (2019), a non-linear paper based on the method of generalized moments in a system, suggests that debt has a positive and large effect on economic growth in the West African Economic and Monetary Union, but that debt accumulation can have a negative effect. Additionally, it demonstrates that the eight (8) West African Economic and Monetary Union member states must incur debt in order to achieve economic progress (the budgetary income of these countries is low). However, this debt must not surpass a predetermined limit, or it will have a detrimental effect on economic progress. He continues by arguing that borrowing in one's own currency, rather than a foreign currency, is a better approach to managing debt. As a result, the impact of debt is frequently determined by the investment that it funds. Without a future and well-structured investment, debt repayment may have a harmful effect on the economy. Mencinger, Aristovnik, and colleagues (2014) examined the effect of high public debt on economic

development in the European Union region using a panel estimate of a generalized economic growth model and other model studies published in an economic journal. As a result, they discovered that in all of the models they evaluated, public debt ratios had a direct effect on annual rates of GDP per capita growth. For the old Member States (1980–2010), the anticipated tipping point of public debt to GDP, at which the beneficial effect of public debt accumulation becomes negative, is between 80% and 94%. Between 1995 and 2010, the percentage of new Member States reaching the tipping point ranged between 53 and 54%. As a result, the statement states that the threshold value for old member states is greater than the threshold value for new member states. Matthew and Mordecai (2016) published research in an Asian academic journal on the implications of Nigeria's state debt. They substantiated their findings with annual statistics spanning the years 1986 to 2014. They discovered that the stock of domestic debt is directly related to economic development, while the payment of domestic debt service is substantial but inversely related to Nigeria's economic development, using the augmented Dickey-Fuller test, the Johansen cointegration test, the error correction method, and the Granger causality test. Additionally, the statistics indicate that, whereas foreign debt and external debt servicing have a slight negative correlation with GDP per capita, domestic debt has a considerable positive correlation. When Chiu and Lee (2017) examined the dangers of a state's issues and the effect of public debt on economic development, they identified evidence suggesting there is a correlation between economic growth and debt to varying degrees of a country's risk. They concluded that while increasing debt has an influence on economic development in a high-risk environment, the negative effect of public debt on economic growth is minimal in a low-risk political and financial climate. They continue by stating that increasing public debt in areas with low composite and economic risk may actually aid economic development. On the other hand, due to disparities in financial, political, and fiscal circumstances, nations do not have the same effect on the debt growth relationship. As a result, as a country's economic and political circumstances change, it should incur debt in order to benefit from the changes. Between 1972 and 2009, Pakistan suffered from a tax collection shortfall. Thus, Akram (2011) examines the impact of Pakistan's state debt (a country that cannot support its investments and needs from its budget has to fundamentally resort to debt to achieve its ends). As a result of this research, it is now obvious that when debt is utilized prudently, it may greatly contribute to economic growth, which surely helps with debt repayment. According to some studies, the negative association between foreign public debt and GDP per capita is due to excessive debt, which also applies to domestic public debt. Blake (2015) used quarterly data from 1990 to 2014 and an autoregressive distributed lag model to examine the effect of public debt on Jamaica's economic development. As a result, he uncovers statistics revealing that foreign public debt has a more negative impact on economic growth than previously assumed, affecting more than 100% of economic growth and 55% of GDP. However, it should be recognized that rising domestic public debt may suffocate Jamaica's economic growth and GDP. By and large, the data indicates that public debt has a nonlinear effect on economic growth in Jamaica.

3 Presentation of data and methodology

3.1 The data

Panel data is an excellent methodology for specialist studies in areas like the West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU).

This strategy provides for the control of individual and/or temporal heterogeneity as well as the capture of dynamic effects on agent behavior. Panel data offers more flexibility and precision, as well as the ability to take into account unobservable aspects. They also offer the advantage of minimizing multicollinearity across variables, allowing more degrees of freedom and boosting performance. These are useful for studying change dynamics because they allow for the gathering of both immediate and long-term effects. Indeed, considering individual and historical data enables us to better comprehend and explain the many factors that drive growth. The data in our app comes from the databases of the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF). 2010 to 2019 has been chosen as the time span.

Our model's variables are as follows:

a) The endogenous variable: The GDP/capita is the explanatory variable, and a positive fluctuation indicates that the economy is growing.

b) Debt is the explanatory variable, which is expressed as a %age of GDP. According to economic theory, a positive coefficient should be expected up to a certain point.

c) The following are the control variables:

-Inflation rate: Most research indicates that this variable has a negative impact on economic activity.

- The country's degree of openness to the rest of the world: this is the ratio of exports to imports divided by GDP.

- Domestic credit to the private sector as a proportion of GDP: the literature prefers a positive coefficient for this variable.

- Foreign direct investment (FDI) is an investment made by a company or person in a business in another nation.

- Life expectancy is reduced at birth...

3.2 Panel modeling requirements

The majority of threshold panel modeling research is focused on either Hansen's PTR (Panel Threshold

Regression) or Gonzalez et al PSTR's (Panel Smooth Threshold Regression) models (2005). Models that illustrate a range of connection regimes between two or more variables are known as these. In Hansen's (1999) model, the transition from one regime to the next is quick. In the PSTR model, rather of providing an indicator, the transition from one regime to another is achieved gradually (smoothly) using a continuous transition function.

Because PSTR modeling seems to be more thorough, we use it to assess the non-linearity between public debt and economic growth. Indeed, as compared to Hansen's PTR definition, the PSTR analysis has a number of advantages (1999). For example, the elasticity of the explained variable with respect to the explanatory variable may vary not just over time but also between locations depending on the threshold variable. PSTR modeling takes into account the unpredictability of the relationship between the explained variable, the explanatory variable, and the transition variable.

We consider the following PSTR model:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \lambda t + \beta_0 X_{it} + \beta_1 X_{it} G(q_{it}, \gamma, c) + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where $i = 1, \dots, N$ is the number of individuals and $t = 1, \dots, T$ determines the analysis period, Y_{it} is the dependent variable (the Gross Domestic Product per capita), α_i and λt the vectors of the individual country and time fixed effects respectively.

X_{it} contains the explanatory variable (%age of debt to gross domestic product). Several other control variables are inserted into the X_{it} matrix. These are the variables likely to explain the debt which are: the inflation rate, school enrollment primary, foreign direct investment, and population, domestic credit granted to the private sector, trade openness rate, life expectancy, CPIA transparency, accountability and corruption in the public sector. In equation (1), $G(q_{it}, \gamma, c)$ is the continuous and normalized transition function associated with the threshold variable q_{it} (ii) with the threshold parameter c and (iii) with a parameter smoothing γ . β_0 and β_1 respectively denote the vector of the parameters of the linear model and of the non-linear model, ϵ_{it} a vector of the error terms iid.

The normalized transition function $G(q_{it}, \gamma, c)$ takes values in the interval $[0, 1]$ and allows the system to gradually switch from one regime to another. In order to define the functional form of this transition function, Gonzalez et al. (2005), as well as Granger and Terasvirta (1993), Terasvirta (1994), Jansen and Terasvirta (1996), suggest to retain the following logistic form of order m :

$$G(q_{it}, \gamma, c) = (1 + \exp(-\gamma \prod_{j=1}^m (q_{it} - c_j)))^{-1}$$

Where, $\gamma > 0$ and $c_1 < c_2 < \dots < c_m$. Here, $c_j = (c_1 \dots c_m)$ is a vector grouping the threshold parameters. For $m =$

1 the model has two extreme regimes distinguishing the low values of q_{it} from its high values. γ is a positive parameter that describes the transition from one regime to another. As it approaches infinity, the function approaches an indicator function $I(q_{it} > c_j)$ which takes the value 1 if $q_{it} > c_j$. Moreover, when γ tends towards 0, the transition function becomes a homogeneous linear panel with fixed effects. Indeed, a too high value of γ brings us back to a model à la Hansen (1999) with a sudden transition.

Given the threshold effect introduced by the transition function G , the sensitivity of the dependent variable with respect to the explanatory variable of country i at date t is given by the following expression:

$$S_{it} = \frac{\partial Y_{it}}{\partial X_{it}} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 G(q_{it}, \gamma, c)$$

Equation (3) above shows that the sensitivity of the dependent variable with respect to the explanatory variable can be considered as a combination of the coefficients β_0 and β_1 obtained in the two extreme regimes. Therefore, the definition of the transition function imposes two scenarios:

- If $0 < G(q_{it}, \gamma, c) < 1$, for $\beta_1 < 0$, we will have $\beta_0 + \beta_1 < S_{it} < \beta_0$; and
- If on the other hand $\beta_1 > 0$, we have: $\beta_0 < S_{it} < \beta_0 + \beta_1$.

If γ is high enough, the PSTR is reduced to a two-speed threshold model (PTR model). Thus, the direct effect of the variable of interest on the endogenous variable is β_0 for individuals whose variable of interest is below the threshold and $(\beta_0 + \beta_1)$ for individuals whose variable of interest is greater than the threshold.

The first step in estimating a PSTR is first to check the non-linearity.

To do this, González et al. (2005) propose a test which consists in comparing a linear model to a PSTR model. Indeed, when $\gamma = 0$, then the function $G(\cdot)$ has the value $1/2$ whatever the value taken by the threshold variable. The threshold effect therefore disappears and the model is nothing more than a linear panel. It is the same when $\beta_1 = 0$.

Considering the fact that under the null hypothesis, the model contains nuisance parameters (Davis, 1987), González et al. (2005), propose to replace the transition function $G(q_{it}, \gamma, c)$ by its Taylor expansion of order 1 in the neighborhood of $\gamma = 0$.

For m regimes, the equation to be estimated then becomes:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \lambda t + \beta_0' X_{it} + \beta_1' q_{it} X_{it} + \dots + \beta_m' q_{it}^m X_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Testing the linearity hypothesis for m regimes ($\gamma = 0$) again amounts to testing:

$$H_0 : \beta'_1 = \beta'_2 = \dots = \beta'_m$$

In the case of two regimes (m = 1):

$$H_0 : \beta'_1 = \beta'_2$$

The implementation of such a test is done through the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) and its statistic is:

$$LM = \frac{TN(SSR_0 - SSR_1)}{SSR_0} \sim \chi^2(K)$$

$$LM = \frac{(SSR_0 - SSR_1)/mK}{SSR_0/(TN - N - m(K+1))} \sim F(mK, TN - N - m(K+1))$$

An extension of these tests is generally carried out on the principle of the pseudo-likelihood ratio (pseudoLRT) by Colletaz and Hurlin (2006). The statistic for this test is as follows:

$$\text{pseudoLRT} = -2 [\log(SSR_0) - \log(SSR_1)] \sim \chi^2(mK)$$

Where, SSR₀ is the sum of the squares of the residuals of a linear model with individual effects, SSR₁ is the sum of the square of the residuals of the unconstrained model (PSTR). Under the null hypothesis, the LM statistic is distributed according to a chi-square law with mK degrees of freedom ($\chi^2(mK)$) where K is the number of explanatory variables and m the number of regimes.

However, when the sample size is small, González et al. (2005) propose to use an alternative LMF statistic which is distributed under the null hypothesis according to a Fisher law F (mK, TN - N - m (K + 1)). This test makes it possible to reject or not the hypothesis of linearity in favor of a PSTR model, but also to determine an "optimal" value of the transition variable. According to González et al. (2005), this value is the one that minimizes the p-value of the linearity test.

3.3 Descriptives Statistics of variables

Table 1 below shows the descriptive data for these distinct parameters. The average level of GDP throughout the sample investigated is around 0.7 %, while the average debt of the GDP is 346.7 %, according to the descriptive analysis of these variables. Incoming and outgoing foreign direct investment had an average proportion of 77.9% and -129.6%, respectively.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the panels data

	LCPI	LDC	LDEBT	LFDIN	LFDIO	LGDP	LINFLA	LLIE	LPOP	LSCH	LTRA
Mean	1.138763	2.998082	3.466517	0.778672	-1.29596	-0.00747	0.156931	4.086094	16.52103	4.532572	4.093614
Median	1.098612	2.977928	3.505557	0.742714	-1.24781	-0.13524	0.262364	4.08522	16.64485	4.463658	4.079579
Maximum	1.252763	3.692947	4.171306	2.934802	3.487306	0.81978	1.902108	4.215824	17.06265	4.886332	4.683119
Minimum	0.916291	2.294786	2.687847	-4.0043	-6.38005	-0.72532	-1.60944	3.981922	15.67519	4.197487	3.591537
Std. Dev.	0.12017	0.33904	0.306761	0.989589	1.948673	0.434883	0.946859	0.052033	0.393565	0.208532	0.252863
Skewness	-0.64383	-0.31087	-0.28294	-2.1251	0.133242	0.276165	-0.33439	0.56604	-0.76032	0.428199	0.664968
Kurtosis	2.293004	2.710911	3.152708	13.66738	3.715072	2.201057	2.35745	3.245811	2.532247	1.905872	3.139093
Jarque-Bera	4.046087	0.881507	0.644154	247.2325	1.091891	1.768833	1.61276	2.516303	4.745893	3.61975	3.352642
Probability	0.132252	0.643551	0.724642	0	0.579294	0.412955	0.446471	0.284179	0.093206	0.163675	0.187061
Sum	51.24432	134.9137	155.9932	35.04025	-58.3182	-0.33614	7.061893	183.8742	743.4465	203.9657	184.2127
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.635395	5.05771	4.140497	43.08859	167.0824	8.321432	39.44787	0.119129	6.815301	1.913375	2.813337
Observations	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45

3.4 Correlation analysis variables

Table 2: Results of the correlation

LCPI	LDC	LDEBT	LFDIN	LFDIO	LGDP	LINFLA	LLIE	LPOP	LSCH	LTRA
1										
0.1418094	1									
0.3527727		1								
0.2377531	0.6358874		1							
0.1157975	2.68E-06			1						
0.2440767	0.2174689	0.2056751			1					
0.1061409	0.1512835	0.1752812				1				
0.2555725	0.3160629	0.2384158	0.2775877				1			
0.0901784	0.034421	0.1147553	0.0648657					1		
0.0835204	0.2321803	0.3416145	0.3429296	-0.169136					1	
0.5854369	0.1248472	0.0216354	0.0211036	0.2666991						1
0.0763256	0.0429897	0.2809039	0.0763289	0.0942971	0.0182985					
0.6182531	0.7791719	0.0615998	0.6182377	0.5378027	0.905033					
0.4757399	0.2108448	0.1916265	0.0013468	0.14309		-0.163162				

					0.1002784						
0.0009568	0.1644454	0.2073013	0.9929944	0.3483971	0.5122016	0.2842052	-----				
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
0.233316	0.3923997	0.0598775	0.2291814	0.6012741	0.2093565	0.067877	0.240975			1	
0.122961	0.0076738	0.6960055	0.1299321	1.25E-05	0.1675138	0.6577433	0.1107973	-----			
	-		-		-		-				
0.0631036	0.4101971	0.2703717	0.1105466	0.5498506	0.261765	0.0975046	0.0387456	0.7235979			1
0.6804781	0.0051328	0.0724483	0.469728	9.14E-05	0.082389	0.5239971	0.8005046	1.96E-08	-----		
	-										
0.5545434	0.6474966	0.3672083	0.0260699	0.3928682	0.080695	0.156026	-0.206281	0.5806689	0.447077		1

7.73E-05	1.53E-06	0.0130883	0.8650182	0.0075951	0.5982309	0.306078	0.1739853	2.89E-05	0.0020774		--

3.5 Unit root tests on analysis variables

To avoid spurious regression, we verify the stationarity of our model's variables. To the extent that our methodological framework allows for the possibility of unobservable heterogeneities between individuals in our sample, we employ the Im, Pesaran, and Shin-IPS (2003) test, which specifies the inclusion of heterogeneities under the alternative hypothesis of the absence of a unit root on the one hand, and the Levin, Lin, and Chu-LLC (2002) test, which maintains panel homogeneity under the alternative hypothesis of the absence of a unit root on the other. A single star indicates one important level, two stars indicates two significant levels, and three stars indicates three significant levels (1 significant level of 1 %, two significant levels of 5 %, and three significant levels of 10 %).

Table 3: Panel unit root test results in Level and 1st Difference

Variables	Levels		1st Différence	
	IPS	LLC	IPS	LLC
LCPI	0.23412	-1.47207***	-1.88817**	-2.46357*
LDC	-1.91524**	-4.52845*	-1.85518***	-4.34508*
LDEBT	1.13900	-0.76415	-3.99746*	-8.72316*
LFDIN	-1.95242**	-2.20720*	-4.35495*	-8.77160*
LFDIO	-5.08058*	-11.9633*	-7.93729*	-14.0662*
LGDP	-1.44307***	-4.19460*	-3.88276*	-8.97217*
LINFLA	-0.32466	-2.65571*	-4.55068*	-10.3578*

LLIE	-11.2538*	-23.0540*	-0.88724	-10.6087*
LPOP	-11.8698*	-15.1191*	-6.67366*	-4.66655*
LSCH	-1.04320	-3.38035*	-1.37774*	-3.25700*
LTRA	-074991	-2.87522*	-2.80139*	-6.05890*

4 Presentation of the result and interpretation

The table below summarizes the estimation results for this model. We can see that, depending on the evolution of debt, the relationship between debt and economic growth in the WAEMU is non-linear. When the debt %age is less than or equal to the threshold value of 60.3 %, debt has a negative effect on GDP of 0.4 %, which is negligible, whereas when the debt %age is less than or equal to the threshold value, debt has a positive effect on GDP of 14.6 %, which is significant at 5%. Due to the fact that the signs of the two regimes diverge, we might claim that debt and economic growth are not linear (one is positive and the other is negative). SCH (primary school enrollment) has a GDP coefficient of 1.6 % and is statistically significant at 1%. Foreign direct investment inflow (FDIN) has a negative 4.32 % effect on GDP and is statistically significant at 5%, whereas foreign direct investment outflow (FDIO) has a positive 7.62 % effect on GDP and is statistically significant at 5%. Domestic credit has a negative coefficient of 1.03 % on GDP and is statistically significant at 5%, whereas CPI (transparency, accountability, and corruption in the public sector) has a negative coefficient of 0.6 % on GDP and is statistically insignificant at 5%. LIE (life expectancy) has a connection of 3.7 % with GDP, which is negligible. TRA (trade) accounts for 1.11 % of GDP, which is significant given that GDP accounts for 5% of GDP. While both INFLA and POP have positive GDP coefficients, POP's is statistically significant at 1%, while INFLA's is not.

Table 4: Estimation Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DEBT < 60.299999 -- 62 obs				
DEBT	-0.003761	0.008388	-0.448344	0.6558
C	-4.447753	1.733031	-2.566459	0.0133
60.299999 <= DEBT -- 2 obs				
DEBT	0.146483	0.063278	2.314917	0.0247
C	-13.66259	3.441436	-3.970027	0.0002
Non-Threshold Variables				
CPI	0.006069	0.201525	0.030117	0.9761
DC	-0.010270	0.011414	-0.899738	0.3725
FDIN	-0.043250	0.023418	-1.846898	0.0706

FDIO	0.004468	0.015765	0.283393	0.7780
INFLA	0.043349	0.027548	1.573566	0.1218
LIE	0.036895	0.023278	1.584984	0.1192
POP	9.29E-08	1.67E-08	5.555759	0.0000
SCH	0.016193	0.003792	4.270630	0.0001
TRA	0.011115	0.005448	2.040327	0.0465

Table 5: Coefficient Confidence Intervals

Variable	Coefficient	90% CI		95% CI		99% CI	
		Low	High	Low	High	Low	High
DEBT < 60.299999 -- 62 obs							
DEBT	-0.003761	-0.017813	0.010291	-0.020600	0.013079	-0.026204	0.018683
C	-4.447753	-7.351073	-1.544432	-7.926957	-0.968548	-9.084861	0.189356
60.299999 <= DEBT -- 2 obs							
DEBT	0.146483	0.040475	0.252491	0.019447	0.273519	-0.022831	0.315797
C	-13.66259	-19.42798	-7.897209	-20.57157	-6.753624	-22.87092	-4.454268
Non-Threshold Variables							
DC	-0.010270	-0.029392	0.008852	-0.033185	0.012645	-0.040811	0.020272
CPI	0.006069	-0.331542	0.343680	-0.398508	0.410647	-0.533154	0.545293
FDIN	-0.043250	-0.082482	-0.004019	-0.090263	0.003763	-0.105910	0.019409
FDIO	0.004468	-0.021944	0.030879	-0.027183	0.036118	-0.037716	0.046652
INFLA	0.043349	-0.002802	0.089500	-0.011956	0.098654	-0.030362	0.117060
POP	9.29E-08	6.49E-08	1.21E-07	5.93E-08	1.26E-07	4.82E-08	1.38E-07
LIE	0.036895	-0.002102	0.075891	-0.009837	0.083626	-0.025390	0.099179
TRA	0.011115	0.001989	0.020241	0.000178	0.022051	-0.003461	0.025691
SCH	0.016193	0.009841	0.022546	0.008581	0.023806	0.006048	0.026339

5 Conclusion

This article studies the influence of debt on economic growth using annual data from 2010 to 2019 and a panel of the eight (8) WAEMU member countries. Using the smooth transition panel (PSTR) technique, we demonstrate that there is a non-linear relationship between public debt and growth in WAEMU.

When debt hits an average of 60.3% of GDP, the non-linearity becomes apparent. Government debt's sensitivity has a negative effect on growth below this threshold and a positive effect beyond it.

The estimations are re-examined by integrating critical institutional components in the initial model (in particular inflation, foreign direct investment, corruption, trade, etc.). When the institutional context is included, our findings remain consistent.

As a result, the findings demonstrate that the WAEMU states rely on debt to stimulate economic growth, but they may also serve as a stimulus for subregional governments to reevaluate their development plans in light of other factors other than debt.

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